

Technical Note

Workflow and Conventions for using Tropy to Annotate Instances of Ajami in West African Manuscripts

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Coleman Donaldson

Ajami Lab – CSMC, University of Hamburg

1. Open your project in Tropy.
2. Double-click a manuscript.
3. Rotate and zoom to view the manuscript photos as necessary
4. Take notes regarding an entire photo by simply clicking on the photo and typing in the note box. You can right click in the note box text entry area to “show line numbers” if you are working on a full transcription of a photo. If not, you can free-form enter a note as you wish. There are no recommendation conventions at this time.
5. When you encounter a potential or definite instance of Ajami, annotate it by doing the following: create a “selection” (in Tropy parlance) of a particular photo by selecting the “Selection Tool” and clicking and dragging over the photo coordinates of interest. The “selection” will appear nested under its photo with the name “Selection” (Fr: *Sélection*). Change the selection name using the following convention: ManuscriptCode_### (e.g., “AD05_01” would be mean the Ajami instance 01 in manuscript “AD05”)
6. Each selection also carries its own note which can be accessed simply by clicking on the selection. Fill out the selection note using the following convention: If the selection is an instance of Ajami, the following conventions are recommended: Line 1 = typesetting of Arabic script with a semi-colon at the end; Line 2 = transliteration into Latin script in angle brackets (pick one transliteration system as your convention and be consistent) with a semi-colon at the end; Line 3 = interpretation in Latin-based orthography with a semi-colon at the end; Line 4 = gloss inside of single quotes with a semi-colon at the end. For example:

لنبرو;
<lnbrū>;
lénburu;
'citrus fruit';

If you can't or do not want to fill out a line, make sure to put in a placeholder. Use the following conventions:

AR;
TR;
IN;
GL;